

STUDIES ON FLUXED-CORED ARC WELDING PERFORMANCE OF G17CRMOV 5-10 MATERIAL FOR STEAM TURBINE CASTING**Tiancheng An,***Master student of E.O. Paton Institute of Materials' Science and Welding, National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Ukraine; Engineer of Harbin Turbine Company Limited, China***Yulong Guo***Master student of E.O. Paton Institute of Materials' Science and Welding, National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Ukraine; Engineer of Harbin Turbine Company Limited, China***Abstract**

G17CrMoV5-10 is a maturely used low alloy heat-resistant steel, which is mainly used in high temperature parts such as steam turbine casing and emergency shut valve shell with working temperature less than 570 °C. It's welding performance is poor and the reheat crack tendency is serious after welding. The requirement of the welding heat cycle and welding operation are strict. As an efficient and high-quality welding method, FCAW (Fluxed-cored arc welding) has been widely used in pressure vessels, petrochemicals, power plants and other industries. It is proposed to repair castings made of G17CrMoV 5-10 by FCAW for the serious defects. Confirm the selection of welding materials and designing the welded joint structure of simulated repair welding to verify the feasibility and safety of this method. Confirm the important parameters (such as welding current, welding voltage, preheat temperature, interpass temperature, PWHT) during the welding process to determine welding process parameters for repair welding and conduct simulated welding test for defect repair welding. Perform non-destructive inspection (Ultrasonic inspection or Magnetic particle examination) and destructive testing (such as tensile test, bending test, impact test and metallographic examination) to verify the performance of the welded joints. Confirm that FCAW can be used for welding repair of 17Cr1Mo1V material castings by evaluating the performance of welded joints. Then obtain welded joints with the same microstructure as the base materials and the excellent mechanical properties.

Keywords: G17CrMoV5-10; FCAW; welding; welding Performance.

Introduction

G17CrMoV5-10 (EN10213-2) is a ferritic low alloy thermal strength cast steel. It has good comprehensive mechanical properties at room temperature and good thermal strength^[1]. Its mechanical properties, tensile strength, yield ratio and other properties at room temperature are slightly higher than G10CrMo9-10^[2] cast steel which commonly used in steam turbines and its casting performance is good. Therefore, it is widely used in steam turbine cylinders, quick closing valves, nozzle chambers, steam chambers and other hot components with operating temperatures between 530 °C and 570 °C. G17CrMoV5-10 is limited by the casting process, and it is easy to produce casting defects such as shrinkage porosity and sand holes after casting. In the process of daily production and manufacturing, it often involves operations such as repair welding of casting defects. Due to the nature of high-temperature and high-pressure working conditions, the requirements for welding quality are extremely important. In addition to SMAW, TIG, GMAW used for welding G17CrMoV5-10 castings, FCAW (Fluxed cored arc welding)^[3] has high deposition efficiency, good operability and accessibility, good fluidity of the welding pool, good resistance to the environment, and good protection of the weld pool area^[4]. The welded joint is widely used in the modern welding field due to its excellent mechanical properties and other characteristics. In this paper, the welding of G17CrMoV5-10 castings

by FCAW is tested and studied, the appropriate welding process parameters are explored, and the comprehensive properties of welded joints are verified and evaluated to guide the repair welding of G17CrMoV5-10 castings in the production process.

1 Welding process establishment

The main influencing factors in the process of welding process test are: the properties of the base materials (chemical composition and mechanical properties), the selection and properties of welding materials, the parameters of welding electrical properties (current and voltage), the welding heat input (welding speed), and the welding thermal cycle parameters (preheating, interpass temperature, stress relief heat treatment). This paper confirms the above welding process parameters one by one. Finally, the welding process for the test was established.

1.1 Determination of base metal

G17CrMoV5-10, as a mature low alloy heat strength steel, is widely used around the world. It is an excellent cast steel material for steam turbines. Its corresponding international brands, such as ASTM A356 Gr.9, have been widely used in the field of steam turbines. The base material used in this test is G17CrMoV5-10 casting test plate customized according to the relevant enterprise standards according to the actual product needs, See Table 1 for the relevant chemical composition and Table 2 for the mechanical properties.

Table 1

Chemical composition of base metal								
material trademark	element content (Wt) %	C	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	V
G17CrMoV5-10	Min	0.15	0.50	-	-	1.20	0.90	0.20
	Max	0.20	0.90	0.020	0.015	1.50	1.10	0.30
	element content (Wt) %	Si	Ni	Cu	Al	Sb	As	Sn
	Min	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Max	0.60	0.30	0.30	0.025	0.0035	0.015	0.020

Table 2

Mechanical properties of base metal						
material trademark	R _{P0.2} (MPa)	R _m (MPa)	A (%)	Z (%)	A _{kv} (J)	HBW
G17CrMoV5-10	≥440	590-780	≥15	≥40	≥27	160-220

1.2 Welding material determination

Welding material selection is based on the principle of equal chemical elements and equal strength grade. At the same time, combined with the welding material selection experience of traditional GMAW welding method and the welding material selection standard of FCAW^[5], E81T1-B2 welding wire under AWS A5.29 system was finally selected as the welding material for the test. E81T1-B2 is the standard grade. In terms of the specific welding material selection, after comprehensive analysis and comparison of the performance of corresponding welding materials produced by mature international welding material manufacturers,

K-81T1B2 welding material produced by Korea Koryo Welding Material Company (KISWEL) is selected for welding process test.

K-81T1B2 is a 560MPa strength FCAW cored welding wire with 1.25%Cr-0.5%Mo chemical composition, which is designed for pressure vessels, boiler steam pipes and other places. It has good crack resistance, thermal strength, creep fracture strength, and good welding operability, and can be used for welding in all positions^[6]. The typical chemical composition of all-weld metal of K-81T1B2 welding material is shown in Table 3, and the mechanical properties of all-weld metal are shown in Table 4.

Table 3

Chemical composition of all weld metal of welding materials (Wt) % ^[6]								
Type of shielding gas	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Fe
CO ₂	0.05	0.44	1.08	0.008	0.009	1.25	0.53	Bal

Table 4

Mechanical properties of all weld metal of welding materials				
Welding material brand	Value source	R _{P0.2} (MPa)	R _m (MPa)	A (%)
E81T1-B2	AWS A5.29	≥470	550-690	≥19
K-81T1B2	KISWEL by Measured ^[6]	531	600	25

1.3 Welding structure design

This test fully simulates the actual situation of defect elimination and repair welding of castings. The 300x400x40mm specification base material test plate is selected as the test material. A 30mm deep U-shaped

welding groove with R12 bottom edge and 45° symmetrical center is opened in the middle of the 300x400mm end face along the 400mm length direction. See Figure 1 for the welding structure model.

Figure 1: Welded structure model

During the welding test, the welding shall be carried out at 1G position with 99.90% pure CO₂ gas protection, gas flow of 20-25L/Min, and single electrode multi-layer multi pass welding.

1.4 Determination of welding electrical parameters

Electric characteristic parameters such as current and voltage during welding operation were selected and confirmed by referring to relevant literature [7] and

welding process parameters of the same group of similar materials that were mature in the early stage. Finally, the welding electrical parameters in the test process were confirmed by referring to the FCAW welding parameters of G10CrMo9-10 materials that were qualified in the early stage. The welding process was in the form of droplet transfer [8]. The specific welding electrical parameters are shown in Table 5 below:

Table 5

Electric characteristic parameters for welding operation

Number of layers	Specification of welding wire	Current polarity	Electric current (A)	Voltage (V)
1	φ1.6mm	DCRP	180-260	22-30
2-Cover	φ1.6mm	DCRP	200-300	25-37

1.5 Determination of welding thermal cycle parameters

G17CrMoV5-10 has poor welding performance [9]. In order to prevent cracks after welding and ensure the mechanical properties of welded joints, the preheating temperature and interpass temperature should be strictly controlled during welding. At the same time, in order to obtain the expected microstructure, eliminate welding residual stress and obtain the expected mechanical properties after welding, stress relief heat treatment should be carried out after welding [10]. Due to the high content of Cr, Mo and V elements in the base material, according to the reheat crack sensitivity formula: $CS = \%Cr + 3.3 \times (\%Mo) + 8.1 \times (\%V) - 2$ anal-

ysis, the calculated CS value of G17CrMoV5-10 material has a strong tendency to reheat crack, The parameters of post weld stress relief heat treatment shall be strictly controlled. Therefore, based on the analysis of heat treatment temperature of base material performance, heat treatment parameters of similar materials and relevant data [11, 12], the heat cycle parameters selected in the welding test process are as follows: preheating above 200 °C, interpass temperature 150-300 °C, stress relief heat treatment immediately after welding, heat treatment temperature 690 °C ± 5 °C, holding for 8h, temperature rise rate 80 °C/h, temperature drop rate 60 °C/h, and air cooling after cooling to 300 °C, The thermal cycle curve is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Thermal cycle curve of welding process

2. Performance verification of welded joints

The performance verification of the welded joint of the test piece shall be carried out by combining non-destructive testing and destructive testing. Non destructive testing is carried out by means of ultrasonic flaw detection+magnetic particle flaw detection. The destructive test refers to the relevant requirements of 《

ASME BPVC.IX ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code, Volume IX, Welding, Brazing and Bonding Assessment》. The tensile, bending, impact, hardness and other mechanical tests are carried out on the welded joints, and the metallographic examination is carried out through the metallographic microscope. See Figure 3 for the sample sampling location.

Figure 3: Distribution of sampling locations for destructive tests

2.1 Nondestructive testing

The acceptance standard of welded joints in this test shall refer to the acceptance standard of product body. The main reference standard is «ASME-V Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code -Nondestructive Examination». The acceptable level of flaw detection of

welded joints shall be determined according to the requirements of enterprise standards for casting base materials. See Figure 4 for test panels that have been welded and ground to meet the flaw detection conditions.

Figure 4: Test plate after welding

Conduct ultrasonic flaw detection for the test. The equipment used for ultrasonic flaw detection is HS511 digital ultrasonic flaw detector. Angle probe is used to conduct ultrasonic flaw detection with detergent as coupling agent. The ultrasonic inspection results show that there are no linear defects such as cracks in the weld area, and there is a local air hole defect with a diameter of about ϕ 2mm, the flaw detection results meet the requirements of corresponding standards, and the ultrasonic flaw detection is qualified.

Magnetic particle flaw detection shall be carried out for the welded joints of the test panel and the area within 50mm on both sides by reference. The equipment used for magnetic particle flaw detection is CEW-6000 magnetic particle flaw detector. Black water magnetic suspension and DC current shall be used for flaw detection. Magnetic particle flaw detection shows that there are no cracks, air holes and other welding defects

on the surface and near surface of the weld and nearby areas, and the magnetic particle flaw detection is qualified.

2.2 Destructive test results

2.2.1 Tensile test

Four groups of tensile tests at room temperature were carried out on welded joints to verify the tensile strength of the joints. The test bars were processed and prepared according to ISO6892-1 Metallic materials-Tensile testing- Part1: Method of test at room temperature. The sampling locations are shown in Figure 3. The AGS-X-800KN universal test machine was used for the test. The test environment temperature was 20 °C and the humidity was 18%. The fracture samples after the tensile test were shown in Figure 5. The tensile test results are shown in Table 6:

Table 6

Tensile test results

Sample code	Sample specification (mm×mm)	Loading force KN	Breaking strength MPa	Fracture location	Test result
FT1	25.01×30.01	479	643	Base metal	Qualified
FT2	25.01×30.02	477	635	Welding metal	Qualified
FT3	25.02×30.02	485	646	Welding metal	Qualified
FT4	25.00×30.01	482	631	Base metal	Qualified

The tensile test results show that the tensile fracture of FT1 and FT4 specimens and the base material show that the strength of the welded joint is better than that of the base material body. Although FT2 and FT3 specimens fracture in the weld area, their tensile strengths are 635 MPa and 646 MPa in the range of 590

MPa to 780 MPa of the design strength of the base material. The tensile strengths of FT2 and FT3 content the design requirements of the base material. The test data can prove that the comprehensive tensile properties of welded joints have met or exceeded the requirements of the base material, and the tensile test results are qualified.

Figure 5: Tensile test specimen

2.2.2 Bending test

The cold bending test at room temperature shall be carried out for the welded joints. The specimen shall be processed in the form of side bending and the lateral bending test shall be carried out. The bending test shall

be carried out using the WE-600 hydraulic universal material testing machine. The sampling location is shown in Figure 3, the specimen after the test is shown in Figure 6, and the bending test results are shown in Table 7:

Figure 6: Bend test specimen

Table 7

Bending test results

Test type	Sample code	Test result	Result determination
Side bending	FC1	After bending 180 °, observe that the curved surface of the sample is free of any defects	Qualified
	FC2	After bending 180 °, observe that the curved surface of the sample is free of any defects	Qualified
	FC3	After bending 180 °, observe that the curved surface of the sample is free of any defects	Qualified
	FC4	After bending 180 °, observe that the curved surface of the sample is free of any defects	Qualified

2.2.3 Impact test

The room temperature V-shaped impact test shall be carried out on the welded joints. Three groups of V-shaped impact samples shall be taken respectively from the base metal, the weld center area, the fusion line, the position where the fusion line deviates from the base metal by 2mm, and the position where the fusion line deviates from the base metal by 5mm. The sample size

is 55mm × 10mm × 10mm, the sampling location is shown in Figure 3. The test is conducted at 20 °C, and the three impact values are recorded at each location and the average value is taken for judgment. PTM2200 impact test is adopted for impact test. See Table 8 for sample location and code, and see Figure 7 for test result data.

Table 8

Location and code of 20 °C V-shaped impact test specimen

Sample code	Sample position	Impact energy requirements
FB	Base metal area	27J
FW	Weld center	
FF	Fusion line	
FF2	Offset of fusion line 2mm	
FF5	The fusion line is offset by 5mm	

Figure 7: Results of 20 °C V-shaped impact test

It can be found from the impact test results that under the control of the welding electrical parameters and welding thermal cycle parameters specified in this test, the impact values of the weld, fusion line and heat affected zone of the test sample are relatively stable and far higher than the design requirements of the base metal, and the impact properties of the welded joints are good.

2.2.4 Hardness test

As the thickness of the welding area is up to 30mm, during the welding thermal cycle, the high temperature of the molten pool generated during the welding of the next layer of weld bead will cover the upper layer of weld bead, resulting in a self tempering effect similar to the tempering treatment. Therefore, for the

hardness inspection of the welding joint with large thickness, the layered inspection method is adopted. The area 5mm from the root of the weld bead and 5mm from the upper end of the weld bead is used as the hardness inspection area, with the loading pressure of 500g and hold the pressure with 15 seconds, According to the fusion line position of metallographic corrosion, manually move the indenter along the same line to select 3 points at each position for microhardness measurement, and conduct microhardness inspection on base metal, heat affected zone, fusion line, weld and other areas. See Fig. 8 for the schematic diagram of inspection location, Table 9 for hardness inspection results and Fig. 9 for data analysis.

Table 9

Hardness Inspection Results

Inspection point	Inspection position	Hardness value HB
1、 2、 3	Base metal 1	231、 232、 232
4、 5、 6	HAZ 1	219、 213、 208
7、 8、 9	Weld bead 1	198、 202、 205
10、 11、 12	HAZ 2	220、 208、 215
13、 14、 15	Base metal 2	230、 222、 219
16、 17、 18	Base metal 3	224、 218、 231
19、 20、 21	HAZ 3	215、 223、 209
22、 23、 24	Weld bead 2	200、 208、 195
25、 26、 27	HAZ 4	216、 220、 223
28、 29、 30	Base metal 4	234、 230、 232

Figure 8: Distribution Diagram of Hardness Inspection Points

Figure 9: Hardness Data Analysis Chart

It can be seen from Fig. 9 that the hardness value decreases gradually in the base metal area, heat affected area and weld area due to the influence of welding heat input, and the hardness value in the weld area is far lower than that of the base metal.

The hardness value of the weld and heat affected zone is lower than that of the base metal, which indicates that the internal welding residual stress of the welded joint after post weld heat treatment has been fully released, which proves that the design of welding thermal cycle parameters in this test is reasonable. The hardness value of the fusion line area is significantly higher than that of the adjacent areas on both sides. This is because the liquid molten pool at the fusion line is in direct contact with the unmelted solid base metal. The metal conducts heat to dissipate heat, and the cooling

speed is extremely fast, so its cooling rate is far higher than that of other areas. The residual stress and stress concentration are easy to occur at the fusion line position, so the hardness value is high. This area is the weak area of the entire welding joint.

2.3 Metallographic examination

The metallographic microscope is used to inspect the metallographic structure of the welded joint. In combination with the characteristics of the weak zone of the fusion welded joint, the microstructure analysis is focused on the parts near the fusion line and the heat affected zone. The microstructure of the base material area is shown in Figure 10 (a), the microstructure of the weld area is shown in Figure 10 (b), and the microstructure of the heat affected zone is shown in Figure 10 (c).

Figure 10: Metallographic structure photos

Figure 10 (a): Base Material Organization Figure 10 (b): Weld Organization Figure 10 (c): Heat Affected Zone Organization

It can be found from the metallographic photos that the base material structure is composed of pearlite and fine ferrite, and a large number of precipitates are found on the pearlite.

Medium temperature bainite products, ferrite phase and lath arrangement of ferrite and carbide can be observed in the welded joint. Due to the self tempering effect of multi-layer and multi pass welding, the new weld bead will reheat the previously deposited metal, and change the microstructure and grain size. Therefore, the lath structure and average grain size of bainite have also changed significantly.

In the vicinity of the fusion zone, due to the addition of alloy elements of FCAW flux cored wire, during the solid phase transformation in the solidification and cooling stages of the welding pool, the alloy elements dissolve into the austenite structure, reducing the initial temperature of martensite transformation (MS point). Therefore, the microstructure of the heat affected zone (HAZ) is composed of coarser martensite, bainite and ferrite structures. In addition, due to the large heat input in the FCAW welding process, the unmelted base material structure near the fusion line has obvious austenite transformation, with coarse grains, which is a typical welding overheating structure. The mechanical properties of this area are lower than that of the unaffected base metal, and it is the weakest area of the entire welding joint.

3 Concluding remarks

From the above analysis of mechanical properties at room temperature, it can be seen that welding according to various welding process parameters preset in this test can successfully obtain welded joints with good comprehensive mechanical properties and meeting the material design requirements. However, due to the uneven and unstable heat input in the FCAW process, the mechanical properties of welded joints are greatly affected. Therefore, the welding electrical and thermal parameters should be strictly controlled when welding G17CrMoV5-10 with FCAW. The repair welding of G17CrMoV5-10 steel castings can meet the product quality and design expected performance by adopting FCAW under strict control of welding process parameters.

For G17CrMoV5-10 casting steel, FCAW is used for repair welding. Compared with conventional SMAW or GTAW welding, the chemical composition of weld metal can be improved by adding core flux to obtain welded joints with better comprehensive performance, improve production efficiency, and reduce repair unit price. Therefore, FCAW has a wider application prospect and engineering application significance.

References

1. Golański Grzegorz. Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of G17CrMoV5-10 Cast Steel After Regenerative Heat Treatment [J]. *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, 2010, 132(06), 1-5.
2. Pavan A R, Arivazhagan B, Zubairuddin M, et al. Thermomechanical Analysis of A-TIG and MP-TIG Welding of 2.25Cr-1Mo Steel Considering Phase Transformation [J]. *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, 2019, 28 (8) , 4903-4917.
3. Hee-Dae Im, Chang-Hyun Choi, Jae-Heon Jung, et al. The Latest Technology Development Trends of Flux Cored Wire[J]. *Journal of Welding and Joining*, 2016,34 (6) , 1-10
4. Nikola Bajic, RAKIN Marko, VELJIĆ Darko, et al. Analysis of the Quality of the Weld Metal Obtained with Alloyed Flux-Cored Wire [J]. *Advanced Materials Research*, 2014, 3460, 170-175.
5. Kim T H, Park C G. Development of Welding Consumables for GMAW and FCAW [J]. *Journal of Welding and Joining*, 2017, 35 (6) , 96-100.
6. KISWEL. Flux Cored Welding Wire K-81TB2 [EB/OL]. 2020[2021.01] https://en.kiswel.com/product/product_view.asp?id=1501
7. Prajapati P, Badheka V J, Mehta K P. Hybridization of filler wire in multi-pass gas metal arc welding of SA516 Gr70 carbon steel [J]. *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 2016:10426914.2016.1244847.
8. Fangjie Cheng, Fangjie Cheng, Xinjie Di, et al . Arc Characteristic and Metal Transfer of Pulse Current Horizontal Flux-Cored Arc Welding[J]. *Transactions of Tianjin University*, 2017, 23(02), 101-109
9. Arivazhagan B, Vasudevan M. Studies on A-TIG welding of 2.25Cr-1Mo (P22) steel [J]. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, 2015, 18, 55-59
10. Pereira P, Franco C, Filho J G, et al. Hydrogen effects on the microstructure of a 2.25Cr-1Mo-0.25 V steel welded joint [J]. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2015, 40 (47) , 17136-17143.
11. Kumar R, Tewari V K, Prakash S. Oxidation Studies on Base Metal, Weld Metal and HAZ Regions of TIG Weldment in 2.25 Cr-1Mo (T22) Boiler Tube Steel Under Cyclic Conditions.
12. R. D. Fu, Y. Q. Yang, C. Y. Wang, et al. Effects of weld thermal cycles and post-welding tempering on second phase particles in 2.25Cr-1Mo-0.25V steels [J] *Science and Technology of Welding and Joining*. 2008, 13(04), 349-356.